

THE REPRESENTATION AND FUNCTION OF NATURE IN "SHIKASTA" BY DORIS LESSING

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Abstract

This study analyzes ecological elements in the mystical novel "Shikasta" by Doris Lessing emphasizing performative, ecstatic and philosophical functions of nature in the novel. The research employs ecological and philosophical literary approaches to reveal author's aim to demonstrate ecological and moral in humanity and some potential solutions to these problems.

Key words: nature, environmental disaster, planetary landscape, SOWF, mysticism, moral decay.

Introduction. "Shikasta. Re: Colonized planet 5" was written in 1979 by Doris Lessing and it is considered first book of "Conopus in Argos: Archives" series. This novel was written in late twentieth century during the Cold war and emergence of ecological awareness, so it combines science-fiction, spirituality and ecological reflection. The planet called "Shikasta" which means "broken up" symbolizes the Earth, faced both spiritual and ecological disaster. The novel is really influenced by mysticism and Islamic sufism that Doris Lessing was interested in 1960s. While spiritual themes, it also involves deep ecological issues that the planet is not just a background, but it is an active cosmic organism and it is a mirror for the moral and physical decay of human-beings. By this kind of representation, Lessing makes humans be aware of their actions towards nature and its catastrophic consequences.

Methodology. This study employs a qualitative literary analysis to examine the representation of nature in Shikasta. The methodological framework combines ecocritical theory, textual analysis, and contextual interpretation in order to explore how natural imagery, environmental symbolism, and ecological discourse function within the narrative. The approach is interpretive and analytical rather than quantitative, as the purpose of the research is to reveal thematic meanings, narrative strategies, and philosophical implications embedded in the text.

Discussion and Results. Nature in "Shikasta" appears in different forms, such as planetary landscape, energy system of the world, climate and biological life of world. Shikasta is a planet whose ecosystem is depend on the network of energy called "SOWF" ("sowf" (substance-we-are-feeling) is regularly sent by main governor and colonizer planet "Canopus". This energy provides the planet with both ecological health and inhabitants' moral balance. But this energy flow is distracted by another evil force called "Shammat" and the Shikasta begins to face ecological disasters and spiritual decay.

In the novel landscape transforms from being source of living into harshness and Lessing emphasizes animals and nonhuman creatures less than human civilization and its impact on cosmic integration. Humans' moral corruption effects whole systems: seasons and climate lose balance that shows its fatal influence even to time and ecology.

In terms of performative function, nature is not only background or scenery, it can act, react and strongly connected with the fate of humanity. One example is that the breakdown of "SOWF" flow impacts on everything in the planet: climate, time, society and all other creatures. This performative dimension reflects what Lawrence Buell calls the "environmental

imagination"—the idea that the environment can possess narrative agency and shape human destiny [Buell, 1995:84]. Humans in Shikasta became greed and started to be warfare. It is said in the novel: "More than one inhabitant of Shikasta have included creatures so large that one of them could consume the food and living space of thousands of co-inhabitants in a single meal." When it occurred, nature also became rebellious and started to take a revenge from the humanity with natural catastrophe. Cheryll Glotfelty describes this condition as literature's "earth-centered ethics" [Glotfelty, 1996:72], nature is an autonomous moral participant. The imagery of dried rivers, "dying soil" and "contaminated air" shows a clear example for this revenge.

From another point of view, nature has a didactic role in the novel. Through the voice of Jahor, who is sent to the Shikasta to investigate and analyze its condition and most of information are given by his reports, planet's distress is described as a moral lesson in spiritual humility. The unpleasant conditions and events in Shikasta was described through the cosmic lens and it is claimed that all ecological disasters in the planet is the outward expression for inner spiritual breakdown of the inhabitants. According to Susan Rowland: "Once Shikasta has fallen into individualistic Shammah, Johor tries to maintain some ghost of Canopus with his metaphor of SOWF, 'Substance-Of-We-Feeling', which, we are told, he has devised because damaged Shikastan brains can hope to retain nothing else." [Lessing, 1979:23]

Aesthetically, a vast, mystic scale in Shikast is constructed through the imagery and Lessing transformed human experiences into a cosmic allegory. In novel, broken documents, reports and testimonies plays an essential part to show the fragmentation of natural order and the images of fading light, dust, drought render the decline of Shikasta giving apocalyptic tone. Lessing used aesthetic interplay to transform the destruction in the planet into poetic grandeur intertwining beauty and loss. As Greg Garrard notes: "Ecological writing often reworks traditional genres to foreground nonhuman agency" [Garrard, 2012:46], Lessing blends science-fiction and eco-criticism. In this case, nature is both subject and structure by shaping mood, imagery and expressing deep logic of narrative universe.

The novel is completely devoted to spiritual and philosophical ideas, influenced by sufism and holistic science. Considering the planet as a independent system, Lessing emphasizes that human's destructive attitude towards nature is not just ecological but metaphysical and it is the loss of spiritual relationship with nature. Furthermore, "re-colonized planet" symbolizes colonization of the Earth by all negative systems such as rationalism, imperialism and even modernism. In this case, author's message is clear: when people consider the nature sacred and valuable, they will become aware and environmentally friendly.

Conclusion. Nature is represented as a cosmic protagonist in Shikasta and gives a glance to the ecological issues of the Earth from the cosmic sphere. Through the planetary imagery, biological collapse and the disruption of "SOWF" flows, author tries to illustrate the planet as a living system and its health is completely depend on human actions. While nature provides artistic, philosophical, symbolic and performative functions, author envisions ecological restoration as spiritual renewal of both planet and psyche. She invites the reader to see not as an external scenery but also the source of human existence and doing harm to nature is to do harm to humans themselves.

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